

Diastereoselective synthesis of substituted decalins from Rauhut-Currier adducts of conjugated nitroalkenes[†]

Pramod Shanbhag, Vaijinath Mane, Chinmoy Hazra and Irishi N. N. Namboothiri*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Bombay, Mumbai-400 076, India

E-mail : irishi@iitb.ac.in Fax : 91-22-2576-7152

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Abstract : Highly functionalized *trans*-decalins have been synthesized in a diastereoselective fashion via cascade intermolecular Michael-intramolecular aldol reaction involving cyclic ketones and Rauhut-Currier adducts of nitroalkenes under Lewis base/Bronsted acid-catalyzed conditions.

Keywords : Rauhut-Currier (RC) reaction, Michael addition, aldol reaction, decalins, nitroalkenes.

Introduction

Decalins constitute the key structural component of terpenoids, steroids and many other natural products and drug molecules¹. *Trans*-decalins, in particular, are the targets of many synthetic approaches², the Robinson type annulation being the earliest and the most classical one³. Methods such as (double) Michael addition-Claisen/Dieckmann condensation⁴, carbocation-mediated cascade cyclization⁵ and intramolecular Diels-Alder reaction-radical cyclization⁶ have also been employed for the synthesis of *trans*-decalins. Recently, Chen and co-workers reported the formation of decalin carbaldehydes by reacting the Michael adduct of cyclohexanone and nitroalkenes with α,β -unsaturated aldehydes in the presence of diphenylprolinol silyl ether as the chiral catalyst⁷. The desired decalin skeleton was constructed through a two-step procedure from cyclohexanone and each step required a new catalytic system to induce stereoselectivity in the decalins.

From another perspective, Rauhut-Currier (RC) reaction or vinylogous Morita-Baylis-Hillman (MBH) reaction is an elegant approach for making multifunctional molecules via homo- or hetero-coupling of electron-deficient alkenes⁸. As part of the studies by our group and others on the MBH and the RC reactions of nitroalkenes and the synthetic applications of the products⁹, we have

developed the RC reaction of nitroalkenes with methyl vinyl ketone (MVK)¹⁰ and demonstrated the application of the products in the synthesis of cyclopentenones¹¹. Asymmetric intramolecular cyclization of these RC adducts have been reported recently, but with poor enantioselectivity¹². Herein, we wish to report the application of those RC adducts for the construction of *trans*-decalins with absolute diastereocontrol.

Results and discussion

Initially, we have considered all the possible intramolecular cyclization pathways for the Michael adduct **3** resulting from the RC adduct **2** and cyclohexanone **1** (Scheme 1). These include a 6-exo-trig cyclization to give a 6,6-fused bicyclic system decalin **4**, an alternative 6-exo-trig cyclization to give a spirocyclic system **5**, an 8-exo-trig cyclization leading to a 6,8-fused bicyclic system **7** and a different 8-exo-trig mode giving rise to the bridged bicyclic system **6**.

Given the scope of the above Michael addition-intramolecular cyclization strategy, we have treated the RC adducts **2** with cyclohexanone **1** in the presence of proline and different Bronsted acids (Table 1). This is in anticipation that proline would form the enamine of cyclohexanone and the latter's addition to the RC adduct **2** would be facilitated by H-bonding of nitro group with various Bronsted acids. We were also hopeful that the

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Scheme 1. Cascade Michael-Aldol reaction of cyclohexanone **1** with Rauhut-Currier adduct **2**.

initial Michael adduct **3** would cyclize in the same pot under the same conditions in a cascade fashion to afford one of the bicyclic compounds mentioned in Scheme 1, most likely, decalin **4**. However, much to our surprise and disappointment, the reaction of RC adduct **2a** with cyclohexanone **1** in the presence of proline (40 mol%) and various Bronsted acids under neat conditions (entry 1) and in *i*-PrOH (entries 2–3) did not proceed at all. Assuming that this may be due to the shifting of equilibrium from enamine to less reactive oxazolidinone¹³, we employed diphenylprolinol to generate enamine (entries 5–6) because in many proline-catalysed asymmetric reactions, diphenylprolinol was found to be a good substitute for proline⁷. However, the inability of diphenylprolinol also to catalyze the reaction prompted us to screen an achiral amine base such as pyrrolidine (entries 7–10). This time we were amused by the formation of decalin **4a** as a single diastereomer in 68% yield (entry 8).

Subsequently, the scope of the reaction was investigated by subjecting different RC adducts **2** to the cascade reaction with cyclohexanone **1** under our optimized conditions, viz. 40% pyrrolidine and 20% 4-methoxybenzoic acid under solvent-free conditions at room temperature. Thus, RC adducts with strongly electron-donating groups **2a–c** and a weakly deactivating group **2e** afforded the corresponding decalins **4a–c** and **4e**, respectively, in good

Table 1. Catalyst optimization : Decalin synthesis

Entry	Base	Additive	Solvent	% Yield ^{a,b}
1	Proline	TFA	None	No reaction
2	Proline	TFA	<i>i</i> -PrOH	No reaction
3	Proline	4-Methoxy benzoic acid	<i>i</i> -PrOH	No reaction
4	Proline	Benzoic acid	<i>i</i> -PrOH	No reaction
5	Diphenylprolinol	Benzoic acid	<i>i</i> -PrOH	No reaction
6	Diphenylprolinol	Benzoic acid	None	No reaction
7	Pyrrolidine	4-Methoxy-benzoic acid	<i>i</i> -PrOH	61
8	Pyrrolidine	4-Methoxy-benzoic acid	None	68
9	Pyrrolidine	–	None	12
10	Pyrrolidine	4-Methoxy-benzoic acid	THF	17

^aAfter silica gel column chromatography. ^bThe products were single diastereomers.

yields (entries 1–3 and 5). The yields of decalins **4d** and **4g** were moderate (32–42%) in the case of RC adducts with weakly electron-donating and a neutral aromatic substituent, **2d** and **2g**, respectively (entries 4 and 7). The RC adducts with a weakly deactivated aromatic ring **2f** and a heteroaromatic ring **2h** afforded the corresponding decalins **4f** and **4h** in much lower yield (15–22%, entries 6 and 8). The low to moderate yields of the desired decalins **4** encountered in few cases are due to further condensation of the acetyl methyl group of **4** with cyclohexanone **1**. These products were part of the complex mixture and could not be obtained in pure form.

A heterocyclic analog of cyclohexanone **1**, viz. Boc-protected 4-piperidone **8**, also reacted with a selected RC adduct **2a** to provide aza-decalin **9** as a single diastereomer in moderate yield (35%, Scheme 2).

The structure and stereochemistry of decalins **4a–h** and octahydroisoquinoline **9** were determined by detailed NMR analysis of a representative compound **4b**. The most deshielded C–H proton appearing at δ 4.75 as a doublet of triplet (J 11.7 and 4.0 Hz) was assigned to H-4 based on ¹H-¹H COSY analysis. The almost equal (dd collapsed

Table 2. Substrate scope : Decalin synthesis

Entry	Ar	4	Time (h)	% Yield ^a
1	a : 4-OMe-C ₆ H ₄	4a	3	68
2	b : 3,4-(OMe) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	4b	3	73
3	c : 3,4-OCH ₂ O-C ₆ H ₃	4c	3	58
4	d : 4-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	4d	4	32 ^b
5	e : 4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	4e	3	65
6	f : 4-Br-C ₆ H ₄	4f	4	15 ^b
7	g : C ₆ H ₅	4g	3	42 ^b
8	h : 2-Furyl	4h	8	22 ^b

^aAfter silica gel column chromatography. ^bThe low yield is due to further condensation of 4 with 1. But the condensation product could not be isolated in pure form.

to t) and strong diaxial coupling (J 11.7 Hz) of H-4 with H-2 (δ 2.61) and H-5 (δ 3.38) together with a weak coupling (J 4.0 Hz) with H-3 (δ 2.25) confirmed this assignment. Further, the strong NOE for H-4 with H-3, H-1 and a peak in the shielded region ($\sim\delta$ 1.40), presumably H-6, confirmed the *cis*-relationship of these four protons. The fact that H-5 (δ 3.38) has only diaxial coupling (dd collapsed to *t*, J 11.4 Hz) suggests that H-6 is also axial. This in turn suggests that Ar, NO₂ and CH₃CO occupy equatorial positions rendering conformational stability to the cyclohexane ring. The decrease in the C=O stretching frequency from their normal value (1686–1698 vs \sim 1710 cm⁻¹) is indicative of an intramolecular hydrogen bonding for the carbonyl with the OH group. This would be possible only if the OH group is axial suggesting that the decalin skeleton is *trans*-fused. Thus, the detailed spectroscopic analysis confirms the *trans*-fusion in decalin and the relative stereochemistry of all the substituents.

Fig. 1. Stereochemical assignment based on NMR analysis of decalin 4b.

The room temperature ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra of decalins 4 showed broad signals for the aromatic protons and carbons, respectively, indicating certain unusual dynamic phenomenon due to restricted rotation of the aromatic ring. Therefore, NMR spectra were recorded for a representative compound 4d at different temperatures, 313 K, 273 K and 233 K, besides room temperature (\sim 293 K). Two broad signals with equal intensity observed for the aromatic protons at room temperature (293 K) resolved to a broad ABq at 313 K. This appeared like a broad triplet at 273 K and later resolved to a complex but symmetrical AA'BB' type multiplet. Examination of the aromatic region of the ¹³C NMR spectrum also revealed similar unusual temperature dependence. Only three signals were visible for the aromatic carbons at 293 K and 313 K. However, lowering the temperature to 273 K led to emergence of a total of six signals, in which two were intense and the remaining four less intense. Further lowering the temperature to 233 K resulted in all the six signals appearing with similar intensities. This temperature-dependent dynamic phenomenon appeared on ¹H and ¹³C NMR time scale is indicative of the anisotropic effect experienced by the aromatic protons and carbons due to restricted rotation about the Ar-C bond. Detailed NMR studies on this phenomenon will be reported in due course.

Fig. 2. Variable temperature ¹H and ¹³C spectra for decalin 4d.

The proposed mechanism for the diastereoselective formation of *trans*-decalin with well-defined relative stereochemistry for the substituents is attributable to the formation of a chair-like transition state in which Ar, NO₂ and the enamine moiety are equatorial (Scheme 3). Stereoselective axial protonation by the Bronsted acid and intramolecular aldol reaction by attack of the enamine from the equatorial face of the C=O group leads to the formation of *trans*-decalin with absolute diastereoselectivity.

Scheme 3. Proposed mechanistic model for the observed diastereoselectivity.

Conclusions

We have developed a method for the highly diastereoselective synthesis of *trans*-decalin starting from cyclohexanone and Rauhut-Currier adducts of conjugated nitroalkenes under Lewis base/Bronsted acid catalysed conditions. Although the yields are not excellent at present, the reaction is a superior alternative to the existing methods in terms of diastereoselectivity and step economy. Further scope of this reaction, including asymmetric version, is currently being investigated and will be reported in due course.

Experimental

General: The melting points recorded are uncorrected. NMR spectra (¹H, ¹H decoupled ¹³C, ¹³C-APT, ¹H-¹H-COSY and ¹H-¹H-NOESY and HSQC) were recorded with TMS as the internal standard. The coupling constants (*J* values) are given in Hz. High resolution mass spectra were recorded under ESI Q-TOF conditions. The RC adducts **2** were prepared by literature methods¹⁰.

General procedure for the synthesis of decalin **4 and octahydroquinoline **9**:**

To a stirred mixture of RC adduct **2** (1 mmol) and cyclohexanone **1** or piperidone **8** (6 mmol, excess), pyrrolidine (28 mg, 0.4 mmol, 40 mol%) and *p*-

methoxybenzoic acid (30 mg, 0.2 mmol, 20 mol%) were added and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature. After the completion of the reaction (monitored by TLC), the solvent was evaporated and the residue was purified by silica gel column chromatography by eluting with 15–25% EtOAc : hexane mixture to afford the pure decalin **4** or **9**.

1-(8a-Hydroxy-4-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-nitrodecahydronaphthalen-1-yl)ethanone (4a):

Colorless solid; yield 68% (235 mg); m.p. 241–243 °C;

IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3516 (br, vs), 2930 (m), 1698 (m), 1602 (s), 1554 (s), 1516 (m), 1381 (m), 1253 (m), 1032 (w); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 0.98–1.71 (9H, m), 2.23 (1H, ddd, *J* 11.6, 4.2, 3.2 Hz), 2.28 (3H, s), 2.60 (1H, ddd, collapsed to dt, *J* 13.1, 11.6 Hz), 2.73 (1H, dd, *J* 13.1, 3.2 Hz), 3.39 (1H, t, *J* 11.6 Hz), 3.50 (1H, d, *J* 1.3 Hz), 3.76 (3H, s), 4.72 (1H, ddd collapsed to td, *J* 11.6, 4.2 Hz), 6.82 (2H, br, unresolved), 7.03 (2H, br, unresolved); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 21.0, 24.8, 25.9, 29.7, 32.1, 37.1, 46.8, 48.0, 55.3, 55.7, 70.8, 90.7, 130.2, 159.0, 213.4; MS (ES⁺, Ar) *m/z* (rel intensity) 370 (MNa⁺, 100), 323 (10), 283 (8), 239 (8); HRMS (ES⁺, Ar) calcd. for C₁₉H₂₅NO₅Na (MNa⁺) 370.1630, found 370.1639.

1-(4-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-8a-hydroxy-3-nitrodecahydronaphthalen-1-yl)ethanone (4b):

Colorless solid; yield 73% (275 mg); m.p. 215–217 °C; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3508 (br, vs), 2936 (s), 2855 (m), 1694 (s), 1594 (vs), 1559 (vs), 1520 (s), 1367 (s), 1263 (vs), 1143 (m), 1026 (m); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 0.98–1.71 (8H, m), 2.25 (1H, ddd, *J* 11.7, 4.0, 3.2 Hz), 2.28 (3H, s), 2.61 (1H, ddd collapsed to dt, *J* 13.0, 11.7 Hz), 2.75 (1H, dd, *J* 13.0, 3.2 Hz), 3.38 (1H, dd collapsed to t, *J* 11.7 Hz), 3.50 (1H, s), 3.84 (6H, s), 4.75 (1H, ddd collapsed to td, *J* 11.7, 4.0 Hz), 6.61 (1H, br,

unresolved), 6.67 (1H, br, unresolved), 6.79 (1H, br, unresolved); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 21.0, 24.7, 25.9, 29.8, 32.1, 37.0, 47.2, 48.1, 55.6, 56.0, 70.8, 90.6, 111.9, 114.9, 116.6, 148.8, 213.4; MS (ES^+ , Ar) m/z (rel intensity) 378 (MH^+ , 32), 360 (53), 313 (100); HRMS (ES^+ , Ar) calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{28}\text{NO}_6$ (MH^+) 378.1917, found 378.1924.

*1-(4-(Benzod[*d*][1,3]dioxol-5-yl)-8a-hydroxy-3-nitrodecahydronaphthalen-1-yl)ethanone (4c)* :

Colorless solid; yield 58% (209 mg); m.p. 222–224 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3454 (br, vs), 2926 (m), 2854 (w), 1695 (m), 1594 (vs), 1558 (s), 1443 (m), 1384 (w), 1351 (m), 1256 (m), 1041 (m); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 1.02–1.74 (9H, m), 2.23 (1H, ddd, J 11.5, 4.1, 3.0 Hz), 2.28 (3H, s), 2.61 (1H, ddd collapsed to dt, J 13.1, 11.5 Hz), 2.72 (1H, dd, J 13.1, 3.0 Hz), 3.40 (1H, dd collapsed to t, J 11.5 Hz), 3.51 (1H, s), 4.68 (1H, td, J 11.5, 4.1 Hz), 5.93 (2H, s), 6.50–6.80 (3H, br, unresolved m); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 21.0, 24.7, 25.9, 29.9, 31.4, 32.1, 37.0, 38.3, 47.3, 55.6, 70.8, 90.6, 101.2, 213.4; MS (ES^+ , Ar) m/z (rel intensity) 384 (MNa^+ , 100), 297 (47), 253 (32), 227 (49), 223 (18), 135 (14); HRMS (ES^+ , Ar) calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{23}\text{NO}_6\text{Na}$ (MNa^+) 384.1423, found 384.1434.

1-(8a-Hydroxy-4-(4-tolyl)-3-nitrodecahydronaphthalen-1-yl)ethanone (4d) :

Colorless solid; yield 32% (105 mg); m.p. 194–196 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3480 (br, s), 2934 (s), 2852 (w), 1692 (s), 1561 (vs), 1377 (m), 1210 (w), 815 (w); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 0.94–1.74 (9H, m), 2.25 (1H, ddd, J 11.7, 4.1, 3.2 Hz), 2.27 (3H, s), 2.29 (3H, s), 2.60 (1H, ddd collapsed to dt, J 13.1, 11.7 Hz), 2.74 (1H, dd, J 13.1, 3.2 Hz), 3.40 (1H, dd collapsed to t, J 11.7 Hz), 3.49 (1H, s), 4.74 (1H, ddd collapsed to td, J 11.7, 4.1 Hz), 7.01 (2H, br, unresolved), 7.08 (2H, br, unresolved); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 20.9, 21.2, 24.8, 25.8, 29.7, 32.1, 37.0, 47.2, 47.8, 55.6, 70.7, 90.6, 124.4, 129.6, 131.4, 135.2, 137.2, 213.5; MS (ES^+ , Ar) m/z (rel intensity) 354 (MNa^+ , 100), 267 (80), 223 (88), 197 (45); HRMS (ES^+ , Ar) calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{25}\text{NO}_4\text{Na}$ (MNa^+) 354.1681, found 354.1667.

1-(4-(4-Chlorophenyl)-8a-hydroxy-3-nitrodecahydronaphthalen-1-yl)ethanone (4e) :

Colorless solid; yield 65% (228 mg); m.p. 179–181 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3517 (br, vs), 2930 (m), 2848 (w),

1698 (m), 1602 (s), 1553 (s), 1516 (s), 1381 (s), 1353 (m), 1253 (m), 1180 (w), 1032 (w), 825 (w); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 0.98–1.74 (8H, m), 2.25 (1H, ddd, J 11.6, 4.2, 3.6 Hz), 2.28 (3H, s), 2.60 (3H, ddd collapsed to dt, J 13.1, 11.6 Hz), 2.73 (1H, dd, J 13.1, 3.6 Hz), 3.45 (1H, dd collapsed to t, J 11.6 Hz), 3.52 (1H, d, J 1.1 Hz), 4.77 (1H, ddd collapsed to td, J 11.6, 4.2 Hz), 7.07 (2H, br unresolved), 7.26 (2H, br unresolved); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 20.9, 24.8, 25.8, 29.7, 32.0, 37.0, 47.0, 47.8, 55.5, 70.6, 90.3, 129.2, 133.5, 137.0, 213.2; MS (ES^+ , Ar) m/z (rel intensity) 374 (MNa^+ , 100), 360 (90), 313 (80), 287 (32), 242 (34), 188 (25); HRMS (ES^+ , Ar) calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{NO}_4\text{ClNa}$ (MNa^+) 374.1135, found 374.1143.

1-(1-(4-Bromophenyl)-decahydro-4a-hydroxy-2-nitronaphthalen-4-yl)ethanone (4f) :

Colourless solid; yield 15% (60 mg); m.p. 175–177 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3475 (br, s), 2933 (s), 2851 (m), 1690 (s), 1554 (vs), 1364 (w), 1207 (vw), 815 (vw); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 0.98–1.71 (8H, m), 2.25 (1H, ddd, J 11.7, 3.9, 3.2 Hz), 2.28 (3H, s), 2.60 (1H, ddd collapsed to dt, J 13.1, 11.7 Hz), 2.74 (1H, dd, J 13.1, 3.2 Hz), 3.44 (1H, t, J 11.7 Hz), 3.54 (1H, s), 4.72 (1H, td, J 11.7, 3.9 Hz), 7.01 (2H, br s), 7.42 (2H, br s); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 20.9, 24.8, 25.8, 29.7, 32.1, 37.0, 47.1, 47.8, 55.5, 70.7, 90.2, 121.6, 132.2, 137.5, 213.2; MS (ES^+ , Ar) m/z (rel intensity) 420 ($[\text{MNa}+2]^+$, 60), 418 (MNa^+ , 60), 349 (30), 289 (47), 252 (100); HRMS (ES^+ , Ar) calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{NO}_4\text{Na}$ (MNa^+) 418.0630, found 418.0616.

1-(8a-Hydroxy-3-nitro-4-phenyldecahydronaphthalen-1-yl)ethanone (4g) :

Colourless solid; yield 42% (133 mg); m.p. 206–208 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 3468 (br, m), 2928 (m), 1694 (m), 1601 (s), 1561 (m), 741 (m); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 0.91–1.75 (8H, m), 2.25 (1H, ddd, J 11.7, 4.2, 3.3 Hz), 2.28 (3H, s), 2.61 (1H, ddd collapsed to dt, J 13.0, 11.7 Hz), 2.76 (1H, dd, J 13.0, 3.3 Hz), 3.50 (1H, t, J 11.7 Hz), 3.53 (1H, d, J 1.2 Hz), 4.77 (1H, td, J 11.7, 4.2 Hz), 7.12 (2H, br m), 7.21–7.28 (3H, br m); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): δ 21.0, 24.8, 25.9, 29.8, 32.1, 37.1, 47.6, 47.9, 55.7, 70.7, 90.5, 127.7, 129.0, 138.4, 213.4. MS (ES^+ , Ar) m/z (rel intensity) 340 (MNa^+ , 100), 298 (20), 209 (25), 167 (10); HRMS (ES^+ , Ar)

calcd. for $C_{18}H_{23}NO_4Na$ (MNa^+) 340.1525, found 340.1529.

1-(8a-Hydroxy-4-(4-furyl)-3-nitrodecahydronaphthalen-1-yl)ethanone (4h) :

Colorless solid; yield 22% (67 mg); m.p. 143–145 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3448 (br, vs), 2928 (m), 1693 (m), 1603 (vs), 1518 (m), 1451 (m), 1351 (m), 1262 (m), 1143 (m), 1025 (m); 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 0.98–1.73 (9H, m), 2.23 (1H, ddd, J 11.7, 3.8, 3.2 Hz), 2.27 (3H, s), 2.59 (1H, ddd collapsed to dt, J 13.1, 11.7 Hz), 2.70 (1H, dd, J 13.1, 3.2 Hz), 3.46 (1H, s), 3.57 (1H, t, J 11.7 Hz), 4.83 (1H, td, J 11.7, 3.8 Hz), 6.10 (1H, dd, J 1.8, 1.6 Hz), 6.24 (1H, d, J 1.8 Hz), 7.32 (1H, d, J 1.6 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 20.9, 25.0, 25.8, 29.3, 32.2, 36.9, 41.6, 46.0, 55.4, 70.5, 87.9, 109.5, 110.3, 142.4, 151.4, 213.4; MS (ES^+ , Ar) m/z (rel intensity) 330 (MNa^+ , 100), 290 (30), 243 (50); HRMS (ES^+ , Ar) calcd. for $C_{16}H_{21}NO_5Na$ (MNa^+) 330.1317, found 330.1317.

Tert-butyl 5-acetyl-4a-hydroxy-8-(4-methoxyphenyl)-7-nitrooctahydroisoquinoline-2(1H)-carboxylate (9) :

Colorless solid; yield 35% (156 mg); m.p. 194–196 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3486 (br, s), 2973 (m), 2934 (m), 1686 (vs), 1612 (w), 1551 (s), 1515 (m), 1425 (m), 1366 (m), 1249 (s); 1H NMR (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.25–1.48 (13H, m), 1.66–1.92 (2H, m), 2.29 (3H, s), 2.31 (1H, ddd, J 11.7, 4.0, 3.1 Hz), 2.55 (1H, ddd collapsed to dt, J 13.1, 11.7 Hz), 2.74 (1H, dd, J 13.1, 3.1 Hz), 3.09 (1H, br s), 3.41 (1H, t, J 11.7 Hz), 3.76 (3H, s), 4.72 (1H, td, J 11.7, 4.0 Hz), 6.80 (2H, br s), 7.25 (2H, br s); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 28.4, 28.6, 29.6, 31.8, 36.3, 42.3, 44.0, 47.1, 54.7, 55.4, 69.4, 79.7, 90.2, 114.5, 154.6, 159.4, 212.9; MS (ES^+ , Ar) m/z (rel intensity) (MH^+ , 20), 393 (100); HRMS (ES^+ , Ar) calcd. for $C_{23}H_{33}N_2O_7$ (MH^+) 449.2288, found 449.2274.

Supporting Information Available

Complete experimental procedures and characterization data and copies of NMR spectra for all the new compounds.

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